

Challenges to Effective Instructional Supervision in Public Secondary Schools of Enugu State

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Abstract

Instructional supervision is the process of ensuring implementation of the educational objectives of a school by overseeing, equipping and empowering teachers to provide meaningful learning experiences for students. It is the process of improving instruction for the benefit of students, it has the ability to disrupt proper teaching and learning if not properly handled. Therefore this study investigated the challenges of effective instructional supervision in public secondary schools of Enugu state. Four research questions four hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey with a population of 9,529 teachers was used for the study. Furthermore, a sample size of 953 teachers representing 10% of the population was used. Multistage proportionate sampling was used for adequate representation of teachers from the six educational zones of the state. A researcher designed questionnaire face validated by three experts from Educational Foundation and Measurement and Evaluation in Enugu State University of Science and Technology respectively was used for the study. Internal consistency was determined using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient with 0.76 obtained from the pilot study. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while t-test statistics tested at 0.05 level of significance was used to analyze the hypotheses. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that instructional supervision should be taken seriously if educational goals and objectives must be achieved. Supervision of instruction should be made compulsory in schools for effective teaching and learning.

Key words: Instruction, Supervision, Effective, Secondary school, Challenges, Students

Introduction

In every delivery of quality services, effective appraisal and supervision must be emphasized. This is fundamental for the effectiveness of such services through improved communications, motivation, cohesion and adequate teamwork. The provision of educational services does not just occur without putting in place adequate measures to ensure the realization of the objectives of education hence school supervision

is an essential educational management control mechanism which ensures the objectives and goals are achieved (Omorobi, 2012). Supervision especially instructional aspect is so important that any school without adequate supervisory mechanism or strategies is bound to fail in its achievement of education goals. This is because for any school to achieve its goal, adequate leadership through constant raise of consciousness of staff must be used as a reminder of the school objectives need for effective discharge of daily duties. However despite adequate and well trained teachers, school plants, instructional materials and funding; effective management of a school cannot be achieved without effective instructional supervision (Omorobi, 2012). Since teaching and learning are complementary process, instructional supervision is required to guide properly. This is because the success of an educational experience depends largely on the performance of the teacher.

The importance of instructional supervision on the achievement of effective learning in modern educational system cannot be over emphasized especially at the secondary school level which is perceived as a vital step for career decision and a period filled with concern and uncertainty considering the falling standard of education in Nigeria. It is noteworthy to state that if education in secondary schools especially in Enugu state is to become functional and self-reliant like what was seen decades ago, greater attention must be paid in the way teachers perform their instructional duties. This is in accordance with the opinion of Ogundele 2004 in Animba (2020) that the ultimate goal of a subject teacher is to prepare and present his/her students with qualitative and quantitative education so that they will not only become functional individuals who are able to become self-reliant through the different skills inculcated in them; but are able to do well both in internal and external examinations. Therefore the importance of instructional supervision lies in the need to enhance quality teaching and learning as advocated in Sustainable Development Goal vision 2016-2030 which projects an inclusive and equitable quality education for the promotion of lifelong learning opportunities for all. Moreover every education stakeholder seeks justification for their direct or indirect investment on education as well as the reason education should remain top priority for the government amidst other competing sectors scrambling for resources. Therefore school managers are expected to ensure constant improvement of the quality of educational services delivered in school during teaching and learning in order to receive this top spot from educational stakeholders. This is because the desired results on students can only be achieved through an established process of supervision. Thus for optimal performance of public secondary schools in Enugu state, intensive instructional supervision must be used in the achievement of school goals and objectives. This is because instructional objectives ensure that teaching and learning are done in a conducive environment and condition in order to yield desired results.

Instructional supervision like other concepts in education do not have a generally accepted definition. This is because it has been defined and seen by different scholars according to insight and perception. According to Wikipedia (2021) the term “Supervision” is coined from two words “Super” (above) and “Videre” (see). This implies a process whereby a person with higher or superior knowledge interacts in a friendly way with another with a lower knowledge in order to improve the effectiveness of a given task. Chike and Okoli (2016) opined that it is the process of bringing improvement in instruction by working with teachers who are closer to the students in order to achieve academic/educational purposes. This was in agreement with Eziuzo (2014) who perceived supervision as the act of providing leadership through a well-structured and designed process in order to help teachers gain better competence in teaching and learning while improving in the general performance of the students. Furthermore, supervision is part of school management which is primarily concerned on the achievement of appropriate instructional expectations of educational system. It is the process of overseeing teachers, students and other staff activities in the process of teaching and learning in order to ensure full compliance with the general accepted principle of education. As a process of enhancing qualitative teaching and learning, instructional

supervision started simultaneously with school supervision during the introduction of western education in Nigeria by European missionaries at Badagry in 1842.

Instructional supervision is the process of bringing about improvement in the teaching and learning process through a network of organized cooperative activities and democratic relationship of persons concerned with teaching and learning (Mohammed, Yusuf & Mbitsa, 2015). Hence instructional supervision is the coordination of different test by autonomous and delegated authority who ensures that personal consideration is excluded from official business with all fairness in the treatment of the teacher. Hence a school instructional supervisor is a representative of the Ministry of Education whose major responsibility includes making the school productive through a system of operational guidance on the critical areas of education process in order to stop wastage in the school process. Instructional supervision is also an internal and external process concerned with regular resource utilization and maintenance of actions that promote effective learning. The role of an instructional supervisor is very crucial in instructional improvement in order to achieve effective teaching and learning in secondary schools hence National Policy on Education (2004) recognizes the need to ensure quality control through regular and continuous supervision of contents, quality and quantity of educational objectives are to be achieved. In every secondary school, the principal as the chief executive is also the main instructional supervisor. This is because part of his responsibility entails planning, organizing, coordinating, supervising, directing and controlling the quality and quantity of services and activities necessary for the achievement of school goals (Animba, 2020). The principal gives leadership in teaching and learning process by coordinating the activities of both tutorial and non-tutorial staff, controls available school plants and improve instructional program of the school. According to Omorobi, (2020), the different forms of instructional supervision are:

a: **Internal supervision**-This employs internal staff members of a school to provide supervisory service to teachers within the school. This form of instructional supervision is usually a daily routine administrative effort towards ensuring that teachers and other non-tutorial staff of a school lives up to school daily expectations by effectively and efficiently performing their duties. It is often carried out by the principal, vice principal, heads of department and other senior and experienced teachers designated by the principal education.

b: **Inter-school visitation**: This is a situation where teachers of different subject area, qualifications and experiences visits other teachers of same category in their b: **External supervision**- This is a form of instructional supervision carried out by officials of the inspectorate division of the Ministry of Education at federal, state and local government levels. These officials are neither staff of a school or familiar with a particular school operations unlike internal supervision. However they provide unbiased routine inspectorate supervisory services to schools through regular school visitations. The various forms of supervision they carry out includes: full supervision, routine supervision, follow-up supervision, partial and sample supervision among others. Some instructional supervisory techniques in secondary schools of Enugu state includes:

a: **Classroom visitation**: It is a situation where a supervisor visits a teacher while in action. The teacher performs his statutory duty which is teaching while the supervisor observes the teaching and pencils down some points of interest both positive and negative which will be addressed later. This is the oldest form of instructional supervision yet the most sensitive technique which must be handled with care. This is because the presence of the supervisor in the classroom can affect the learning outcome positively or negatively. However this gets the supervisor acquainted with the various factors affecting growth and development of education and in making future recommendation and prediction.

c: **Demonstration:** This is a method where a more experienced teacher acts as a supervisor or a professional supervisor prepares series of lesson and activities in order to give a firsthand insight on a particular methodology and concept. This technique is very effective in stimulating growth in teachers and enhances involvement by using systematic observation procedures followed up by different activities. It also gives new and inexperienced teachers the opportunity of seeing the actual and desirable instructional activities being performed by experts. Furthermore, it gives room for sharing of ideas and interaction between the supervisor and supervisee.

d: **Workshops:** This is a technique where a group of teachers come together under one umbrella in order to discuss specific topic, concept, problem area, teaching methodology among others in order to find solution to problem areas. It gives room for face to face interaction between teachers and superior / experienced professional which can result in objective analysis of ideas leading to better result oriented decisions.

e: **Micro-teaching:** This is a technique where a teacher focuses on a selected teaching strategy by scaling down class size, time and other teaching complexities. It is designed in such a way that new skills are developed while old ones are retained with immediate feedback. Microteaching provides opportunity for supervisors and teachers to identify, define, describe, try out, and re-try certain teaching situation. It also gives teachers and supervisors opportunity to try a particular activity of instruction over and over again in order to identify and re-identify the strength and weakness involved in a particular instruction. (Mohammed, Yusuf & Mbitsa, 2015). According to Suleiman (2015), some of the challenges of instructional supervision of secondary schools are:

A: **Financial constraint:** This is as a result of lack or inadequate funds to facilitate school visitation as well as provide the necessary help to teachers by providing and purchasing material resources for instructional supervision of secondary schools. These materials includes vehicles, computers for collecting data, stationeries among others which will help in supervision

B: **Insufficient and lack of qualified supervisory staff:** Most members of the supervisory team in Enugu state lack the necessary proficiency and expertise in supervision. This is because they lack the professional skills and expertise in supervision. Additionally, there is short supply of school supervisors with very large areas of coverage which they cannot cover annually.

C: **Opposition to supervision by teachers:** Many teachers see the concept of instructional supervision as undermining their professional experience and expertise hence they see supervisors as a threat. This is partially due to lack of professionalism in supervision and negative behaviors some supervisor's exhibit during the process. Thus they try to resist supervision to the disadvantage of learners and education sector.

D: **Lack of supervisory structure:** A lot of secondary schools in Enugu state lack mechanism or structures for school internal instructional supervision hence teachers are not supervised periodically until there are visitors from Ministry of Education knocking on the door. This also gives room to poor productivity and ineffective teaching and learning

E: **Poor communication skills:** Many supervisors in the state lack professional managerial skills to handle human being. This is seen in their comments, judgments and behavior. Some treat teachers as subordinates and with lack of respect leading to resistance from teachers. Sometimes they embarrass teachers' in front of the students because they want to show-off or prove they are in charge and powerful as well thereby causing devastation as well as destruction of teacher's morale and motivation. This affect the general job satisfaction of the teacher who also works in the opposition since his performance is not appreciated.

Purpose of study

The main purpose of the study was to identify the various challenges that have limited the effectiveness of instructional supervision in public secondary schools of Enugu state and specifically proffer solutions in order to bring back the lost glory of instructional supervision on teaching and learning for better academic performance of students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- 1: To what extent does teacher variable militate against effective instructional supervision in secondary schools of Enugu state?
- 2: To what extent does inadequate instructional resources militate against instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state?
- 3: To what extent do poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state?
- 4: To what extent do multiple roles of a principal militate against effective instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers of secondary schools in Enugu state on the extent to which teacher variables militate against effective instructional supervision.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers of secondary schools in Enugu state on the extent to which inadequate instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision.

H03: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers of secondary schools in Enugu state on the extent to which poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision.

H04: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers of secondary schools in Enugu state on the extent to which the multiple roles of a principal militate against effective instructional supervision.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. A survey design is one in which generalizations are made over the entire population from a sample population (Uzoagulu, 2013). The design was used because descriptive survey research allows for the description of condition and situation as they exist in their natural setting. The study was conducted in Enugu state Nigeria, A sample of 953 representing 10% of the entire population of teachers in public secondary schools of Enugu state as managed by Post Primary Secondary School Management Board was used for the study (PPSMB, 2018). Proportionate

stratified sampling was further employed to sample 600 females and 353 male teachers from the six educational zones. A researcher designed instrument titled “Challenges of Effective Instructional Supervision in Public Secondary Schools of Enugu State” (CEISPSSE) was used to elicit responses from the respondents. The instrument was face validated by three experts; two from department of Educational Foundation and one from Measurement and Evaluation all from Enugu state University of Science and Technology. The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha and a reliability co-efficient of 0.76 was obtained. A total of 1000 copies of questionnaire was given out while 953 was returned properly filled and subsequently used for analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to analyze the hypotheses. Where the mean is equal to 2.5 or above, the item was regarded as great extent, where the mean was below 2.5, the item was regarded as low extent. Similarly, when the calculated t-value is equal to or greater than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance and appropriate degree of freedom, the null hypothesis was significant and not accepted but when the calculated t-value is less than the critical value the null hypothesis was accepted hence not significant.

Results

Research Question 1a: To what extent does teacher variable militate against effective instructional supervision in secondary schools of Enugu state?

Mean and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which teacher variable militate against effective supervision in secondary schools of Enugu state.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male			Female		
		\bar{X}	SD	DEC	\bar{X}	SD	D
	To what extent does the following teacher variable militate against effective instructional supervision						
1	Poor remuneration of teachers	2.6	0.7	GE	2.7	0.5	GE
2	Poor working condition	2.5	0.7	GE	2.5	0.6	GE
3	Irregular payment of salaries	2.7	0.6	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
4	Unqualified teachers	3.0	0.4	GE	3.0	0.3	GE
5	Lack of basic teaching skill	2.9	0.5	GE	3.0	0.3	GE
6	Wrong placement of teachers	3.1	0.3	GE	2.7	0.5	GE
7	Poor training of teachers	3.0	0.4	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
8	Poor supervision of teachers	2.6	0.7	GE	2.7	0.5	GE
9	Lack of job satisfaction	2.7	0.6	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
10	Poor performance appraisal programs	3.1	0.3	GE	3.0	0.3	GE
	Cluster summary	2.8	0.5	GE	2.7	0.4	GE

Data analysis from table 1a shows that the mean and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which teacher variable militate against effective instructional supervision shows a grand mean of 2.8 for male teachers and 2.7 for female teachers as well as standard deviations of 0.5 for the male and

0.4 for female which signifies that both male and female teachers agree to a great extent that teacher variables militate against effective instructional supervision.

Hypothesis 1

Ho: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers of secondary schools in Enugu state on the extent to which teacher variables militate against effective instructional supervision.

Table 1b: T-test analysis of mean rating scores of female and male teachers on the extent to which teacher variable militate against effective instructional supervision.

Variables	n	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t(cal)	t(crit) value (0.05)	Dec
Male Teachers	353	2.8	0.5		0.03	1.96	HO ₁ Accepted
Female Teachers	600	2.7	0.4	952			

The analysis in table 1b above shows that t-calculated of 0.03 is less than the critical value of t-test which is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis (HO₁) is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which teacher variable militate against instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state. Though the mean scores of male teachers of secondary school (2.8) is greater than that of the female teachers (2.7), the difference is statistically not significant. The teachers did not significantly differ in their opinions in this regard.

Research Question 2

To what extent does inadequate instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state?

Table 2a: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which inadequate instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male			Female		
		\bar{X}	SD	DEC	\bar{X}	SD	D
	To what extent does the following inadequate instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision?						
11	Inadequate classrooms	3.1	0.3	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
12	Inadequate/lack of functional laboratories	2.6	0.7	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
13	Inadequate chalkboards	2.7	0.6	GE	2.7	0.5	GE
14	Lack of teaching aids	2.5	0.7	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
15	Poor road networks	2.7	0.6	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
16	Inadequate vehicles for supervisors	3.0	0.4	GE	2.5	0.6	GE
17	Lack of stationary for reports and feedback	2.5	0.7	GE	3.1	0.3	GE
	Cluster summary	2.7	0.5	GE	2.6	0.4	GE

Data analysis from table 2a shows that the mean and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision has a grand mean of 2.7 for male teachers and 2.6 for female teachers as well as standard deviations of 0.5 for male and 0.4 for female teachers which signifies that both male and female teachers agrees to a great extent that instructional resources militate against instructional supervision.

Hypothesis 2

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which instructional resource militate against effective instructional supervision.

Table 2b: T-test analysis of mean rating scores of female and female teachers on the extent to which instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision.

Group	n	\bar{X}	SD	df	T(cal)	Table value (0.05)	t- Dec
Male Teachers	353	2.7	0.5		0.03	1.96	HO ₂ accepted
Female Teachers	600	2.6	0.4	952			

The analysis in table 2b above shows that t-calculated of 0.03 is less than the critical value of t-test which is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis (HO₂) is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision in public secondary schools of Enugu state. Though the mean scores of male teachers of secondary school (2.7) is greater than that of the female teachers (2.6, the difference is statistically not significant. Hence the teachers did not significantly differ in their opinions in this regard.

Research Question 3

To what extent does poor communication/ relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision of secondary schools in Enugu state?

Table 3a: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male			Female		
		\bar{X}	SD	DEC	\bar{X}	SD	D
	To what extent do the following poor communication/relationship variables militate against effective instructional supervision						
18	Poor teacher-supervisor interaction	2.5	0.7	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
19	Supervisors are not sensitive to teachers needs	2.6	0.7	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
20	Most supervisors like to show superior power through intimidation of teachers	3.0	0.4	GE	2.7	0.6	GE
21	Teachers are always threatened by supervision	2.7	0.6	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
22	Supervisors do not display professional insight into the growth pattern of student	2.9	0.5	GE	2.5	0.4	GE
23	Supervisors motivate teachers to work harder	2.0	0.8	LE	1.9	0.9	GE
24	Teachers are not being honest to supervisors	2.6	0.7	GE	3.1	0.3	GE
25	Supervisors are not consistent in dealing with students	3.0	0.4	GE	2.5	0.6	GE
26	Supervisors show irritability towards teachers	3.1	0.3	GE	2.5	0.6	GE
27	Supervisors are always friendly with teachers	2.0	0.8	LE	1.9	0.9	LE
	Cluster summary	2.6	0.6	GE	2.7	0.6	GE

Data analysis from table 3a shows the mean and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which poor communication/ relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against instructional supervision shows a grand mean of 2.8 for male teachers and 2.6 for female teachers as well as standard deviations of 0.5 for male teachers and 0.3 for female teachers which signifies that both male and female teachers agreed to a great extent that poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision.

Hypothesis 3

H03: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision.

Table 3a: T-test analysis of mean rating scores of female and male teachers on the extent to which poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective supervision.

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T(cal)	Table value (0.05)	Dec
Male Teachers	353	2.8	0.5		0.06	1.96	HO ₃ accepted
Female Teachers	600	2.6	0.3	952			

The analysis in table 3a above shows that t-calculated of 0.06 is less than the critical value of t-test which is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₃) is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which poor communication /relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision.

Research Question 4 To what extent does multiple roles of principals militate against effective instructional supervision of secondary school in Enugu state?

Table 4a: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which multiple roles of principals hinder effective supervision of instruction.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Male			Female		
		\bar{X}	SD	DEC	\bar{X}	SD	D
	To what extent does multiple roles of principals militate against effective instructional supervision						
28	Sometimes office works of the principal hinders their ability to monitor school supervision	2.3	0.5	LE	2.0	0.6	LE
29	Principals attendance to several school meetings consumes most of their supervisory time	2.7	0.3	GE	2.5	0.6	GE
30	Some principals do not motivate teachers	2.0	0.8	LE	2.3	0.5	LE
31	Lack of supervision in lesson delivery by principals	2.7	0.3	GE	2.6	0.6	GE
32	Neglect of instructional improvement in teaching	2.3	0.5	LE	2.7	0.5	GE
33	Poor maintenance of discipline in the school	2.2	0.4	GE	2.1	0.3	LE
34	Most principals are focused on administration only	2.7	0.6	GE	2.6	0.3	GE
	Cluster summary	2.8	0.5	GE	2.7	0.3	GE

Data analysis from table 4a shows the mean and standard deviations of male and female teachers on the extent to which multiple roles of principals militate against effective instructional supervision shows a grand mean of 2.7 for male teachers and 2.5 for female teachers as well as standard deviations of 0.5 for male and 0.3 for female teachers which reveals that both male and female agree to a great extent that multiple roles of principals militate against supervision of instruction

Hypothesis 4

Ho: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which multiple roles of principals militate against effective supervision of instruction.

Table 4b: T-test analysis of mean rating scores of female and female teachers on the extent to which multiple roles of principals militate against effective instructional supervision.

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T(cal)	Table value (0.05)	t- Dec
Male Teachers	353	2.7	0.5		0.04	1.96	HO ₄ accepted
Female Teachers	600	2.6	0.3	952			

The analysis in table 4b above shows that t-calculated of 0.04 is less than the critical value of t-test which is 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{04}) is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent to which multiple roles principals militate against effective instructional supervision.

Discussion of Findings

Data from table 1 shows that the use of instructional supervision is dependent on teachers hence the null hypothesis was accepted as it was not statistically significant. This implies therefore that if performance must be enhanced, teachers must be treated with all respect they deserve through good salaries, and other motivational measures in order to give their best to teaching and learning. This finding is in agreement with the view of Ulasi (2011) who stated that teachers are the people who can demonstrate special accomplishments or particular abilities which are of interest and value to students and who are also both able and willing to display, discuss or otherwise present attainment before students. Data analysis from table 2 also showed the extent to which inadequate instructional resources militate against effective instructional supervision. This is in agreement with the views of Ikegbusi (2015) who noted that there is no way the school program can be effectively implemented without the use of instructional materials. Furthermore, analysis from table 3 showed the extent that poor communication/relationship between supervisors and teachers militate against effective instructional supervision. In line with the above assertion Shaibu (2016) stressed that good communication and relationship emphasize more on the humanitarian aspect which seek to satisfy the needs of the worker, minimize his frustration, and increase the level of his job satisfaction. Data from table 4 showed the extent to which multiple roles of principals militate against supervision of instruction. This is in line with Babayemi (2006) in Omemu (2017) who further stated that school principal must not only be trained in the act of administration but must be well acquainted with the principles that guides and control instructional process effectively.

Conclusion

Instructional supervision is carried out by instructional supervisors in order to provide guidance, good counsel, support and continuous assessment of teachers for their professional development in the teaching-learning process. However factors like inadequate instructional; materials, teachers, relationship between teachers and supervisors among others hinder this process. Therefore there is need for these obstacles to be removed for efficient and effective supervision.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in the study, these recommendations were made

- 1: Professional supervisors should be used in the business of instructional supervision in in order for adequate proficiency and expertise be used in the achievement of educational goals.
- 2: Supervisors should periodically go for capacity building training in pedagogical and utilization if instructional materials competences so that when they go for instructional supervision in schools, they can cascade the same competences to teachers
- 3: Principals as internal supervisors should give adequate attention to instructional supervision in orderfor compliance, competence and professionalism in lesson preparation and delivery.

References

- Animba, I. E. (2021). Factors Militating against Effective Teaching and Learning of History among secondary school students in Enugu state. *Sapentia foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender studies*. Vol.3 No. 1 March, 2021
- Chike-Okolie, A. (2016). *Application of supervisory techniques*. In Uchendu, C. C. & Basil B. A. (eds) Educational Management. A Guide for Professionals. University of Calabar Printing Press.
- Egbebi, J. O. & Harbau, M. I (2019). *Essentials of Educational Inspection-Supervision and Planning in the era of Globalization*. Zaria: Dolphin press
- Eya, P. E. & Chukwu, L. C. (2012). Effective Supervision of Instruction in Nigerian Secondary Schools: Issues in Quality Assurance. *Journal of qualitative Education*.
- Eziuzo, G. O. (2014). *Secondary School Administration and Supervision*. Jesuit Press
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education* (Revised) Abuja: Government Press
- Ijaiya, N. Y. S (2012). *Management That Matters: Key to sustainable education*. 113 inaugural lecture, University of Ilorin, Ilorin. Delivered September 13th, 2021
- Ikegbusi, N. G. & Iheanacho, R. C. (2016). Factors Militating against Effective Administration of Secondary Schools in Anambra state. *World journal of educational research, Vol 3. No 1*
- Lamidi, M. L. & Afariogun, A. A. (2020). Imperatives of Supervision in attaining Quality Assurance in Nigerian Educational system. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Educational Planning and Administration, 5(2)*, 72-84
- Okorie, O. O. (2010). Education Supervision and Quality Control in Secondary Schools. *European-American Journal*. 1(1), 34-43
- Omorobi, G. O. (2021). *School Supervision and Educational Management in Nigeria*. Ambit Press Ibadan
- Onyeike, V. C. (2016). *Supervision and Organizational Change for Productivity*. Port Harcourt: Pearls Publishers International ltd
- Shuabu, M. (2016). The Principals Supervisory Roles for Quality Education and Effective School Administration of Basic Education School in Nigeria. *World Educational Journal*.
- Suleiman, N. D. (2011). *Role of Parent Teacher Association on Students School plant Provision and Maintenance in Ijumu Local Government Area*. Available at <https://silynow.sswitsweyst.org>.
- Udida, L. A. (2015). *Issues in National Policy on Education in Nigeria*. University of Calabar Press
- Uzoagulu, A. E. (2013). *Practical Guide to Writing Research Project Reports in Tertiary Institution*. Enugu: Cheston limited
- Uzoma Aja-Okorie (2011). Factors Militating against Head teacher's Effective Supervision of Primary Schools in Ebonyi state. *The Nigerian Academic forum*. Vol 21 No 1
- Wikipedia (2021). *Meaning of Supervision*. www.Wikipedia.org
- Yusuf Sulieman., Nike, Y. S. I., Mustapha, A. I. & Okwara U. J. (2020). Issues and Challenges facing the Supervision of Secondary Education in Nigeria in the 21st century. *World Education Forum*. Vol 19 No 2